

The Motivation of Consumer Branding Behaviors and Its Role in Brand Identification (Case Study: Adidas Brand)

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Abstract— Identifying a brand as a consumer's psychological state of understanding, perceiving, and valuing belonging to a brand. In a brand community, a high level of motivation to engage in behaviors with internal and external role can be achieved by integrating the expectations and responsibilities of the brand community created in people. This research was conducted to motivate branding behaviors in consumers and their role in identifying Adidas brand. In this study, variables were evaluated by a questionnaire. A questionnaire was distributed among 385 people from the population of the Adidas brand in Shiraz. The research method was descriptive correlational. To answer the questions and to investigate the research hypothesis using Smart-PLS software, structural equation analysis and path analysis using partial least squares (PLS) were used. The results of this research indicate that attachment and self-confidence have a positive and significant effect on the behavior within the consumer role in branding. The results of this research also confirm the positive and significant effect of self-esteem and one's autonomy on consumer redundancy behavior in branding. The results also show that behavior in consumer role and consumer redistribution behavior in branding has a significant effect on brand identification.

Keywords— Psychological Needs, Internal role Behaviors, Brand Identity, Adidas Brand.

I. INTRODUCTION

How to create a strong brand has been raised in recent literature as a major issue (Lin, 2015; Voorhees et al, 2015). Since customer retention tactics, including frequent programs and other customer loyalty schemes, have been widely used to create customer loyalty, the effectiveness of this approach has been questioned. Some researchers even describe repeating brochures as "a failure in competitive strategy". Since brand identity helps consumers develop a strong brand relationship through brand identification, recently, scientists have suggested corporate brand identity management represents an important special aspect of a brand name (Balmer et al, 2009). In the past two decades, marketing researchers have re-examined the principles of consumption and proposed different forms of it, for example, one's transactions are complemented by community-based experiences (Mathwick et al, 2008). Usage experiences in the community are also increasingly evident with brands. Social brands allow consumers to form a community, and accept a brand away from geographical constraints, based on an organized set of social relationships (Muñiz and O'guinn, 2001). The expansion of the Internet has created more access to brands for consumers around the world. As a result, groups with online

business brands have become more popular and social media has changed in the field of consumption (Johnson and Lowe, 2015; Singh and Sonnenburg, 2011; Smith et al, 2012). Today, many consumers regularly spend more than one-third of their hours on social media (Adler, 2014), so it's not surprising that online community participation is more than usual. Interestingly enough, members of the brand community do not have many, and they simply share their information or send comments on topics. But they often actively support the brand and work in favor of the brand community.

Affiliates of various business communities, such as San Jav, Jeep, Apple, Coca-Cola, Nike and Volkswagen, have made a brand in the social networking industry, making their brand more famous. These practices are inherently motivating members of the community, and they do not expect direct rewards from companies (Mathwick et al, 2008). Despite their documentary works and their growing display in social media, many companies have not yet fully captured some of their potential marketing potential in brand communities. How can companies motivate consumers in their own interests? More importantly, how can such an incentive are influenced by the role of consumers in the brand community, after which the consumer will be identified with that brand?

To answer this important question, one should familiarize himself with new marketing concepts such as brand identification. The concept of customer brand identification offers a comprehensive understanding of how customer brand relationships are developed (Bhattacharya and Sen, 2003; He et al, 2012). Brand identification is defined as a consumer psychological state of understanding, appreciation, and value of belonging to a brand (Lam et al, 2010; 2013). The brand relationship literature shows that consumers do not buy brands just because they work well. People also buy brands because of the meanings that branding brings to their lives (Fournier, 1998) and to express their own ideas (Sirgy, 1982). In the wider consumer context, empirical studies show that the identification of a company or brand increases the use of the product and the frequency of re-purchasing (Kuenzel and Halliday, 2008). In other words, strong brand identification often leads to increased consumer protection and brand promotion. Contrary to conventional commercial research, where brand identification is generally thought to open up to real concepts and behaviors, the research proposal is helpful in communicating with consumers, and suggests that buying does not need to identify it accurately. In fact, identifying a

brand after it can also be made. This idea is often created when buying new products. In this research, we examine the identification of a brand by a branding behaviors, which includes in-role and transcendental behaviors. As well as one's psychological needs include self-esteem, affiliation and one's autonomy as an introduction to the impact of one branding behaviors on identification brand is introduced. Therefore, in this research, the researcher seeks out what psychological needs affect the identification of the brand by the consumer in terms of the role of mediating in-role and outsider behaviors.

II. THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS

The motivations of branding behaviors in society

Motivation is a stimulant to do something. In this way, a person who does not feel any motivation is called as boring in works, while energetic and active people are motivated and inspirational (Ryan and Deci, 2000). Autonomy suggests that motivation is referred to as natural processes, which is a force to function properly, and this force through satisfaction provides three essential psychological needs: 1) attachment, 2) self-belief, and 3) one's autonomy (Gagné and Deci, 2005). The concept forces us to think that if the satisfaction of these three essential requirements is to be created, the interaction of the members of a brand community with the internal and external roles will increase the brand's behavior. Some of the psychological needs may be in agreement with the internal roles while others are more related to external roles. In a brand community, a high level of motivation to engage in intrinsic behaviors can be achieved by integrating the expectations and responsibilities of the brand community created in people. In general, these conversations are entirely internal, social environments for each person should provide support for both attachment and self esteem. The reason is that, in the expectations and responsibilities of each person, one must: 1) Imagine that these expectations and responsibilities are being appreciated by the people we are in contact with (appreciate).

Research shows that most people always try to be endorsed by others in their values, beliefs, and behaviors, and in this regard, they are related to each other, 2) the effective sense of accomplishment by fulfilling these expectations and doing These tasks are created in person (self-confidence) (Morhart et al, 2009). Therefore, the following hypotheses are presented:

Hypothesis 1: The relation between consumer behaviors in branding has a significant effect.

Hypothesis 2: Self-confidence has a significant effect on the behavior within the consumer role in branding.

On the other hand, for members of a community, expectations and responsibilities beyond what is expected by the community, for example, to participate in extravagance behaviors, should be inherently interesting, enjoyable and satisfying to be imagined. In other words, the motive for doing it is inherent in itself (Gagné and Deci, 2005). In the treacherous behaviors that members try to behave beyond the expectations of the community, there needs to be similar ways to motivate them. Researchers further suggest that it is necessary to develop a person's natural motivation for skills and independence (close to the personal causality). In other words, in order to increase or maintain the intrinsic motive, it

is necessary that: 1) the emotion in which he or she performs relevant behavioral information in the absence of pressure to achieve a particular outcome or in a particular manner (autonomy). 2) Feel that your self-esteem is growing in the social environment. Therefore, the following hypotheses are presented:

Hypothesis 3: Self-esteem has a significant effect on consumer re measurement behavior in branding.

Hypothesis 4: one's autonomy has a significant effect on consumer redress behavior in branding.

Brand identification

According to the social identity theory (Ashforth and Mael, 1989), brand identification is defined as a measure of consumer perceptions of sharing a self-identity feature similar to a brand, including identifying a primary psychiatric state, can be deep, committed, and meaningful relationships that marketers are increasingly seeking to build relationships with their consumers (Bhattacharya and Sen, 2003; Lam et al, 2010). According to previous researches, brand identification as an important structure in branding has three main components: cognitive (sense of membership awareness), evaluation (information related to some appreciated meanings), and emotional (emotional investment in awareness and evaluation). Previous research suggests that members of a brand community constantly use symbols and meanings and brands to build their own identity (Arnould and Thompson, 2005).

First, brand identification processes are carried out and then branding is done through the participation of members in strengthening community behaviors with internal and external roles. For example, when members welcome new users to the community and lead them to important community resources, they are more likely to accept the values and behavioral norms of society as part of their identity. Depreciated behaviors, however, affect the formation of a brand identity in different ways, but the basis of this formation is the strengthening of internal roles. To make things clearer, when members are passionate about celebrating their favorite brands (Muñiz and O'guinn, 2001) or strongly support community cohesion (Mathwick et al, 2008), and certainly with this types of activities acquaints different levels of society with the brand.

These members actively change their individual identities by combining the traditions, meanings, and values of a brand, and more importantly, willingly, as a brand ambassador, the allegiances show their commitment (Muñiz et al, 2009). Therefore, the following hypothesis is presented:

Hypothesis 5: The behavior of the consumer role in branding has a significant effect on brand identification.

Previous research has shown that desirable transactional behaviors are related to the level of identification of a seller with respect to a brand (Hughes and Ahearne, 2010).

Although these findings are well applied to employee issues, there is a clear relationship between the behavior of inertia and brand identification and the level of organizational recognition of employees, acknowledging the desired effects of brand recognition (Hughes and Ahearne, 2010). In this research, we further suggest that the members of a brand community increase their awareness of the brand in question beyond their

divergent behaviors to help branding in society. Therefore, the following hypothesis is presented:

Hypothesis 6: Consumer redressing behavior has a significant effect on brand identification.

Conceptual model

All research studies are based on a conceptual framework that identifies the variables and relationships between them. This conceptual framework is a model by which the researcher based on the relationships between the factors that

are identified in the creation of a major problem. This theory may not necessarily be the researcher's words and reasonably derived from previous research findings about the problem. Since any field research requires a mental map and a conceptual model that is presented in the form of an appropriate analytical tool, the variables and relationships between them, the theory is conceptually shown in Fig. 1, with 6 hypotheses test is visible. Please note that all direct communications are considered positive.

Figure 1: Conceptual Model of Research

III. METHODOLOGY

Methodologically, this research is a correlation research. The research is based on the desirability of obtaining the required data and classification of research according to their purpose. This research is applied as a descriptive-survey method. In this research, a standard questionnaire was used to collect the data needed to test the hypotheses of the research in order to formulate the foundations, definitions and theoretical concepts of the library resources including the literature, books and scientific articles. Information about measuring the data was collected by valid questionnaire.

The questionnaire consists of 23 standard questions, which include 4 self-esteem questions, 4 questions of self-esteem, 3 questions of one's autonomy, 3 questions in-role, 4 interrogative questions, 5 other questions about brand identification, and respondents that they were asked to comment on any question. This questionnaire was developed by Hey et al (2017).

The content of the questionnaire was subjected to the judgment of some of the experts and professors of business and marketing management at universities. After making some corrections and obtaining the confirmation of those professors for the higher reliability and acceptability of formal validity About 30 questionnaires were distributed in the statistical community. Initially, it was not possible to comprehend a number of questions for respondents. After several times the translation of the text of the text and deletion of some of the questions, the questionnaire was sufficiently formal, and finally, the questionnaire agreed data collection tool was used. The statistical population of the research is all Adidas brand customers in the city of Shiraz.

In study, since there is no detailed information on the number of statistical population due to the confidentiality of information and the existence of competition between

manufacturing companies and the provision of clothing and footwear, the statistical society of the study is unlimited, and to estimate the sample size The relative estimation formula is used with a margin of error of 5% and a maximal variance of 50%. Therefore, the number of samples is estimated to be 385.

Findings

In this research, modeling of structural equations using partial least squares method and PLS software has been used to test the assumptions and validity of the model. The PLS is a variance based approach, which requires less constraints in comparison with similar techniques of structural equations such as Laserl and Amos (Liljander et al, 2009). The main advantage is that this kind of modeling requires less number of samples than lasers. It is also considered as a powerful method in situations where the number of samples and items of measurement is limited and the distribution of variables can be indeterminate (Hair et al, 2010). The PLS modeling is done in two steps.

In the first step, the measurement model should be checked through validation and reliability analysis and confirmatory factor analysis. In the second step, the structural model by means of estimating the path between the variables and determining the fitting indexes of the model is examined (Hulland, 1999).

Measurement Model

The measurement model test is related to the validity and reliability of measuring instruments.

To assess the convergent validity, the AVE (mean extracted variance) and CR (composite reliability) criteria were used. The results of this criterion for the dimensions of the six variables of research are shown in Table (1). Composite reliability is higher than 0.7 and mean of variance is higher than 0.5 and two prerequisites for convergent are

valid and structural correlation. As shown in Table (1), all composite reliability values are higher than 0.7 and mean values of variance is higher than 0.5 and this confirms that the

convergent validity of the questionnaire is acceptable at a satisfactory level.

TABLE 1: Average results of variance extracted from research structures

Variable Criterion	Attachment	Self-esteem	One's independence	Inside the role	Renaissance	Brand Identification
AVE	0/634	0/600	0/655	0/737	0/761	0/735
CR	0/844	0/865	0/837	0/882	0/890	0/715

TABLE 2: AVE Ratio Matrix with Structural Correlation Coefficients (Divergent Validity)

	Attachment	Self-esteem	One's independence	Inside the role	Renaissance	Brand Identification
Attachment	0/796					
Self-esteem	0/552	0/775				
Individual independence	0/451	0/601	0/809			
Inside the role	0/387	0/512	0/315	0/849		
Renaissance	0/654	0/428	0/457	0/462	0/872	
Brand Identification	0/479	0/457	0/348	0/581	0/661	0/857

In the divergent narrative, the difference between the indices of a structure and the indexes of other structures in the model is compared. This work is calculated by comparing the root AVE of each structure with the values of the correlation coefficients between the structures. For this, a matrix must be constructed that the values of the main diameter are the root matrix of the AVE coefficients of each structure and the lower values of the main diameter are the coefficients of correlation between each structure with other structures. This matrix is shown in Table (2). As can be seen from the table (2), the AVE of each structure has increased its correlation coefficients with other structures, which suggests the acceptability of the divergent validity of the structures.

Reliability

To examine the reliability of the questionnaire, in addition to the Cronbach's alpha coefficient presented in Table 3, and confirming the reliability of the questionnaire, the PLS method has also been used.

The PLS method uses index reliability (Rivard and Huff, 1988). Indicator reliability is also calculated by measuring the

factor loads by calculating the correlation between the indices of a structure with that structure, which if this value is equal to or greater than 0.6 (Hulland, 1999), it is confirmed that the reliability in the model of measurement is acceptable. However, if the factor load between a question and a related dimension is less than 0.6, then it is possible to delete that question from the model and subsequent analysis. As shown in Fig. 2, all values of factor loads among structures and questions are greater than 0.6, which shows a high correlation.

Structural Model and Hypothesis Test

A structural pattern test examines the hypothesis of research and the effect of hidden variables on each other. To validate the research hypotheses, the Bootstrapping command of Smart PLS software was used to show the output of the coefficients t (Fig. 3). When the values of t in the range is more than 1/96 + and less than 1/96, it is indicative of the significance of the relevant parameter and is subsequently confirmation of the research hypotheses.

TABLE 3: Cronbach Alpha Coefficient

Research structures	Attachment	Self-esteem	Ones' independence	Inside the role	Renaissance	Brand Identification
Cronbach's alpha coefficients	0/846	0/811	0/866	0/854	0/852	0/823

Figure 2: Software output - test model of research (path coefficients and factor load).

Figure 3: Software output - coefficients t

Methods of evaluation of shaping models

One of the ways of evaluating the modeling models is the determination coefficient. The determination coefficient (R2) examines how many percent of the variance of a dependent variable is explained by the independent variable (s). Consequently it is natural that this value is equal to zero for an independent variable and for a dependent variable it is greater than zero. The higher the rate is, the greater the impact factor of the independent variables on the dependent variable is. According to the coefficient of modeling, we can say that the dimensions of attachment and self-esteem have been able to explain 0.428 of the variance of the in-role behavior variable. Furthermore, the dimensions of self-esteem and one's autonomy in general have been able to explain 0.341 of the variance of the variance of retrocession behavior. Intrinsic behavior and evidentiary behavior in general have been able to explain 0.360 of the variance in the brand identification; researchers ranked three values of 0.19, 0.33 and 0.67 as the criterion value for weak, moderate and strong R2 have been introduced. Based on this, it can be concluded that the model has the appropriate predictive capability. The remainder is related to the prediction error and can include other factors affecting in-game behavior, evidentiary behavior, and brand identification.

Answer to hypotheses

According to the results from the path coefficient and t, all the research hypotheses were approved, and the results showed that attachment and self-confidence had a positive and significant effect on the behavior within the consumer role in branding. The results of this research also confirm the positive and significant effect of self-esteem and one's autonomy on consumer redundancy behavior in branding. The results also show that behavior in consumer role and consumer

redistribution behavior in branding has a significant effect on brand identification.

Figure 4: Evaluation of shaping modeling models

IV. CONCLUSION

This research examines the profound understanding of the collective value of collaborative work in brand communities. According to this view, the relationship between consumer motives has been systematically studied and behaviors have been examined with internal and external role in branding and brand familiarity. The findings of a cross-sectional study and a convergent field experiment in relation to the Adidas brand in Shiraz city indicate that members of a brand community, with a sense of belonging and self-belief in the brand community, have a higher interaction in branding with internal role behaviors. While the self-belief and ones' autonomy of self-awareness increase, the interaction of their deviant behaviors is more visible. Contributing to its internal role and its inseparability, in turn, fosters brand identification in the

community. These interesting findings help the existing brand community and have important implications for the Adidas brand. First, our findings offer ways to motivate members of the community as brand representatives, so that they voluntarily defend the brand and promote the brand throughout the brand community. This is the case in all media. The research model shows how much the member does and how it works in internal and external roles. While self-esteem increases the behavior of both roles, the attachment to only the behavior of the inner role, and ones' autonomy increase their extravagance behaviors. This finding provides useful insights on current dogma theory. On the one hand, the results of the research show that, if marketers are aware of the detrimental

or undesirable effects of the removal of members of the community, marketers can well change the community's settings in various ways (for example, most discussions and recent events in the company). In which the members of the community are given less autonomy, as a result of their extra-curricular activities, they are severely undesirable. On the other hand, if marketers find activities with a useful internal role (for example, congratulations to the owners of the company in different ways), conditions may be created to foster the mental need and membership of the community (for example, integration most with social networking sites) to encourage such activities.

TABLE 4: Direct effects, t statistic and outcome of research hypotheses

Theories	Standardized path coefficient β	Statistics t	Mean	Accept or reject the hypothesis
Affiliation → Behavior in the role of consumer in branding	0/455	3/979	Sig<0.05	Accept
Self-confidence → Behavior within the consumer role in branding	0/265	2/000	Sig<0.05	Accept
Self-esteem → Consumer behavior in branding	0/477	4/834	Sig<0.05	Accept
Ones' autonomy → Consumer redressing behavior in branding	0/157	8/273	Sig<0.05	Accept
Intra-consumer behavior in branding → Brand identification	0/504	4/277	Sig<0.05	Accept
Consumer Removing Behavior in Branding → Brand Identification	0/149	8/237	Sig<0.05	Accept

Secondly, the research results help to promote public theory in identifying the brand. While previous research usually examines the relationship between brand identification and consumer behavior (Akerlof and Kranton, 2000; Kuenzel and Halliday, 2008; Hughes and Ahearne, 2010). This study found a "learning sense" in the dynamics model in classic hierarchy exacerbates and offers unique managerial knowledge to help marketers transform brand awareness and behavior into brand recognition, especially when the brand is newly introduced to the market. This is very important because identifying a brand as a key interface will always remain constant against rivals' attacks, thus imposing strong geographic constraints on brand behavior.

Researchers argue that, in order to develop successful brand societies, marketers need the roles of community creators, fostering and facilitating societies by creating the conditions they can improve. Our research shows that a situation for a community is useful and effective in which members of the community are encouraged not to participate in social partnerships from being treated with internal roles in their outsourced behaviors because they are equally helpful in identifying the brand, even if his extravagant behaviors require more interaction and activity. In other words, participation in a brand community, even at a minimal level, helps consumers to better understand brand identity, which provides a positive impact on participation at many levels. Research findings can help prioritize cost and resource allocation in brand management.

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